

Assessment of Myoelectric Controller Performance and Kinematic Behavior of a Novel Soft Synergy-inspired Robotic Hand for Prosthetic Applications

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3 **ABSTRACT**

4 Myoelectric-artificial limbs can significantly advance the state of the art in prosthetics, since
5 they can be used to control mechatronic devices through muscular activity in a way that mimics
6 how the subjects used to activate their muscles before limb loss. However, surveys indicate that
7 dissatisfaction with the functionality of terminal devices underlies the widespread abandonment
8 of prostheses. We believe that one key factor to improve acceptability of prosthetic devices is to
9 attain human-likeness of prosthesis movements, a goal which is being pursued by research on
10 social and human-robot interactions. Therefore, to reduce early abandonment of terminal devices,
11 we propose that controllers should be designed such as to ensure effective task accomplishment
12 in a natural fashion. In this work, we have analyzed and compared the performance of three
13 types of myoelectric controller algorithms based on surface electromyography to control an under-
14 actuated and multi-degrees of freedom prosthetic hand, the SoftHand Pro. The goal of the present
15 study was to identify the myoelectric algorithm that best mimics the native hand movements. As
16 a preliminary step, we first quantified the repeatability of the SoftHand Pro finger movements
17 and identified the electromyographic recording sites for able-bodied individuals with the highest
18 signal-to-noise ratio from two pairs of muscles, i.e. flexor digitorum superficialis/extensor digitorum
19 communis, and flexor carpi radialis/extensor carpi ulnaris. Able-bodied volunteers were then
20 asked to execute reach-to-grasp movements, while electromyography signals were recorded from
21 flexor digitorum superficialis/extensor digitorum communis as this was identified as the muscle
22 pair characterized by high signal-to-noise ratio and intuitive control. Subsequently, we tested three
23 myoelectric controllers that mapped electromyography signals to position of the SoftHand Pro.

24 We found that a differential electromyography-to-position mapping ensured the highest coherence
25 with hand movements. Our results represent a first step towards a more effective and intuitive
26 control of myoelectric hand prostheses.

27 **Keywords:** Prosthetics, Assistive Robotics, Rehabilitative Robotics, Myoelectric Control, Kinematics

1 INTRODUCTION

28 The introduction of myoelectric devices has profoundly modified prosthetics, especially in upper-limb
29 amputation. Upper limb myoelectric devices use electrical activity associated with muscle contraction
30 (electromyographic signals, EMG) recorded from residual muscles in individuals with upper limb loss to
31 control movements of terminal devices, i.e. arm and/or hand prostheses. At the same time, electric actuators
32 address some of the drawbacks of body-powered devices, such as heavy harness and limited functionality
33 [Van Lunteren et al. (1983)]. Furthermore, myoelectric prostheses can offer better aesthetics, greater pinch
34 strength, and ease of operation [Biddiss and Chau (2007)]. However, despite these advantages relative
35 to body-powered devices, the rejection rate of myoelectric prostheses remains very high. Specifically,
36 more than 23% of myoelectric prosthesis users abandon their devices [Biddiss and Chau (2007)]. The
37 main causes for abandonment of myoelectric devices include higher maintenance needs, greater costs,
38 heavier weight, and low intuitiveness of control. These limitations suggest that improving intuitiveness of
39 myoelectric control might contribute to reducing the rejection rate of myoelectric devices. In the present
40 study, we propose that this objective could be attained by improving the correspondence between natural
41 and prosthetic hand movements. The underlying assumption of our proposition is that individuals with
42 upper limb loss might prefer using a prosthetic device that can be controlled using similar muscle activation
43 patterns underlying the control of the native hand, as opposed to being forced to learn abstract EMG
44 patterns to fit the design of the terminal device. This approach could thus play a crucial role for increasing
45 both acceptability and the sense of embodiment, i.e., the sense of the prosthesis becoming part of the
46 users body by transitioning from an extracorporeal to a corporeal structure [Fraser (1984)] [Scarry (1994)]
47 [Murray (2008)].

48 Within the above conceptual framework, anthropomorphism may be an additional factor to be considered
49 to improve users acceptance of myoelectric prostheses, a concept that has been extensively studied in
50 the field of human-robot interaction [Dragan and Srinivasa (2014)] [Bartneck et al. (2009)] [Riek et al.
51 (2009)]. Specifically, myoelectric prostheses represent a category of bi-directional human-robot interactions,
52 as users control the terminal device through muscle activation. To improve effectiveness of prostheses
53 performance, an additional aspect to consider is the correct identification of body sites for the acquisition
54 of EMG through surface electrodes [Micera et al. (2010)]. This is an important factor to ensure optimal
55 EMG signal quality, which in turn is necessary to improve control of the terminal device, while trying to
56 compensate for unavoidable issues such as sweat or movement of the electrode relative to the target site.

57 In the literature on myoelectric prostheses, one can distinguish two approaches: (1) minimalistic mapping
58 for standard one degree-of-freedom (DOF) hand prostheses, where it is customary to use two EMG
59 electrodes located on an antagonistic muscle pair, e.g. residual wrist flexor and extensor muscles, to
60 control the closing and opening of the prosthesis [Ajoudani et al. (2013)] and (2) mapping EMG signals
61 from multiple muscles to multi-DOFs devices (for a survey on the usage of multi-sEMG signals for
62 robotic hand control, the reader is referred to Ison and Artemiadis (2014)). Regarding (1), Ajoudani et al.
63 (2012) examined the incorporation of the users intent in the control command not only in terms of desired
64 motion or equilibrium position but also as stiffness profile estimated on the master side through a suitable

65 human-machine interface. This approach, called Tele-Impedance, was proven to be a viable solution also to
66 overcome stability problems in force reflecting tele-operation and enable a more human-like task execution
67 [Ajoudani et al. (2012)]. Ajoudani et al. (2014) used the major finger antagonist muscle pair, i.e. the m.
68 extensor digitorum communis (EDC) and m. flexor digitorum superficialis (FDS), to map the reference
69 commands by leveraging upon a modified hyperbolic tangent shape. With regard to (2), interfacing EMG
70 signals from multiple residual muscles with a multi-DOF systems requires a direct mapping from multi-
71 EMG patterns to control commands, and this is often accomplished by using machine learning (ML)
72 techniques. However, one of the main issues for a deployment of these methods in clinical settings is its
73 low reliability [Biddiss and Chau (2007)]. To mitigate this drawback, the concept of simultaneous and
74 proportional (s/p) myocontrol was proposed by Jiang et al. (2009), which enables mapping of EMG signals
75 to activation of several DOFs based on regression techniques, rather than a classifier [Ison and Artemiadis
76 (2015)]. Another valuable contribution in this area is the idea of interactive and incremental learning:
77 since calibration of ML methods usually employs a one-shot initial phase, to strengthen its robustness the
78 function approximation can be further refined after this phase, thus leading to a model update that can
79 correct control instabilities [González and Castellini (2013)]; for further details on these topics, the reader
80 is referred to Santello et al. (2016). A different approach consists of invasive myo-controlled prosthetic
81 devices, which combines surgery, bionic reconstruction and engineering, in some cases enhanced by
82 sensory feedback (see for example Ortiz-Catalan et al. (2014), Raspopovic et al. (2014) and Aszmann et al.
83 (2015)).

84 In the present work we focused on the control of the SofHand-Pro (SH-P), the prosthetic myoelectric
85 version of an existing robotic hand, the Pisa/IIT SoftHand (SH) [Catalano et al. (2012)] [Catalano et al.
86 (2014)] [Ajoudani et al. (2014)]. The SH is a humanoid robotic hand that combines the concept of kinematic
87 motor synergies [Santello et al. (1998)], and soft robotics. By combining the concept of hand postural
88 synergies and soft robotics, the result is an artificial system actuated with only one motor, which implements
89 the first human hand synergy in grasping in free hand motion. At the same time, the SH, is also adaptable
90 and robust, and hence able to grasp different types of items. The prosthetic version, the SH-P, can be
91 controlled using two EMG signals from a couple of agonistic-antagonistic (Ag-Aag) wrist or finger muscles.

92 The present study was designed to identify the myoelectric controller that could generate SH-P finger
93 movements with the greatest reliability and degree of similarity of finger movements of the native hand. Our
94 investigation consisted of three steps. First, we quantified the kinematic consistency of SH-P movements
95 across a large number of movements to evaluate the repeatability of its performance. The objective of
96 this evaluation was twofold: (1) to assess the reliability of SH-P response to motor commands, and (2) to
97 ensure that the evaluation of similarity between SH-P and native finger movements would not be biased by
98 random inconsistencies in SH-P response to motor commands. Second, we evaluated the most suitable
99 body sites on the forearm for recording EMG defined in terms of SNR. As described for the first objective,
100 this evaluation was necessary to ensure that myoelectric controllers could be reliably compared by using
101 the best possible EMG signals as inputs to the controllers. Furthermore, high SNR of EMG signals contain
102 greater information about modulation of muscle activity responsible for finger movements, and could
103 therefore be better exploited by the myoelectric controllers. The third evaluation, which is the core objective
104 of the present work, compared three myoelectric control algorithms. The optimal controller was defined as
105 the algorithm that generated SH-P finger kinematics that best resembled finger kinematics of the native
106 hand.

107 Although there is an extensive literature on myo-electric prosthesis controllers (early work dates back
108 to 50's as Battye et al. (1955), for a review see e.g. Castellini et al. (2014)), literature on the use of EMG

109 signals for the control of synergistic movements is moving its first steps. Within this growing framework,
110 it is important to note that the aim of this work is to provide an assessment of myoelectric controller
111 performance and kinematic behavior of a specific device, the SH-P. For these reasons, algorithms were
112 specifically tailored to be used with the SH-P, although other commercial prostheses are endowed with
113 similar controllers. Results of this paper represent a stepping stone towards more in-depth investigation
114 on the extent to which the hardware and software of the SH-P can overcome limitations of existing hand
115 prostheses.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

116 2.1 Participants

117 We performed three experiments. Experiment 1 quantified the repeatability, reliability, and consistency
118 of the SH-P movements. Experiment 2 was designed to identify the agonist-antagonist muscle pair
119 characterized by the highest SNR. Experiment 3 quantified the EMG-to-position mapping algorithm that
120 provided the best correspondence between finger movements of the native hand and SH-P.

121 *Experiment 1* did not involve testing of human subjects as the SH-P was controlled by artificial commands
122 (see below). For *Experiment 2* we tested four able-bodied volunteers (1 female, 3 males; age range: 21-26
123 yrs., mean \pm SD: 22.5 ± 2.06). For *Experiment 3* we tested fourteen able-bodied volunteers (5 females, 9
124 males; age range: 18-27 yrs., mean \pm SD: 20.36 ± 2.43).

125 All subjects were tested on their dominant hand (right hand; self-reported hand dominance). All partici-
126 pants were naïve to the experimental purpose of the study and had no history of neuromuscular disorders.
127 Before data collection, subjects signed an informed consent to participate in the experiment. The experimen-
128 tal protocols were approved by the Institutional Review Board at Arizona State University in accordance
129 with the Declaration of Helsinki.

130 2.2 Apparatus

131 For the present investigation of myoelectric controller algorithms for hand prosthesis, we used the
132 SoftHand-Pro (SH-P) (Fig. 1-A). The SH-P is the prosthetic version of the Pisa/IIT SoftHand (SH), a
133 robotic hand that had been designed for humanoid robots [Catalano et al. (2012)] [Catalano et al. (2014)].

134 The main design concept underlying the development of the SH [Catalano et al. (2012)] [Catalano et al.
135 (2014)] is the construction of a robust, safe, low-cost, and simple robotic hand. The SH finger movements
136 occur along the first hand postural synergy as defined by Santello et al. (1998), i.e., the first principal
137 component extracted from static hand postures used to grasp a wide variety of imagined objects. This first
138 postural synergy was implemented in the SH-P by combining it with a soft-robotics approach, through
139 which a reference position of a “virtual hand” attracts the real hand, thus resulting in the concept of “soft
140 synergy” [Bicchi et al. (2011)]. The soft-synergy approach enables a better control of the interaction forces
141 between the hand and the grasped object, thus allowing the SH-P to grasp a large variety of items.

142 Another important feature of the SH design is that it is underactuated [Birglen et al. (2007)]. Specifically,
143 the SH has 19 DOFs, 4 on each finger and 3 on the thumb, but they are all actuated by only one motor
144 (Fig. 1-A). This feature effectively reduces weight, costs, and control complexity, thus making it an ideal
145 candidate for prosthetics applications since it only requires two EMG signals from an agonist-antagonist
146 muscle pair [Zhao et al. (2015)]. The actuator is a DC motor that pulls a tendon running across the
147 “phalanges” through a system of pulleys. Movements of the SH are controlled using a PID controller,

Figure 1. SH-P used for Experiments 1 and 3. A: Dimensions of SH-P and the main components. B: Markerization protocol (Experiment 1). Note that only the markers placed on the distal phalanges were used for the experiment, whereas additional markers in a triangular configuration were placed on the palm (not visible in this picture).

148 which takes as inputs the desired angular position of the motor and the real position measured by a 12-bit
 149 magnetic encoder (resolution: 0.0875°) applied to the motor. All the structural components of the palm are
 150 built with rapid prototyping material (ABSplus - Stratasys), all the phalanges are fabricated using injection
 151 molding except for the “metacarpo-phalangeal” joint of the thumb which is fabricated using a computer
 152 numeric control machine.

153 The original design of the SH was modified for prosthetic applications. Specifically, the overall size of
 154 the device was reduced to obtain the size of an average human male hand. The electronics were reduced
 155 in size and modified to enable interfacing with commercial EMG electrodes (Otto Bock, Germany). The
 156 electronics, previously placed at the base of the hand, was moved to the back to obtain a more compact
 157 design (Fig. 1-A). The original SH motor (15 Watt Maxon motor RE-max-21 24V) was substituted with a
 158 smaller and lower voltage motor (14 Watt Maxon motor DCX-22-S 12V) and battery. The dimensions of
 159 SH-P used for the present work are 210 mm from the tip of the thumb to the tip of the little finger and 170
 160 mm from the base of the palm to the tip of the middle finger (225 mm relative to the wrist interface). The
 161 thickness of the palm is different between the thumb and the little finger sides of the hand, i.e., 40 mm on
 162 the little finger side, where the EMG connectors are placed, and 53 mm at the motor location (the thumb
 163 side), respectively. The SH-P is powered using an 11.1V AR.Drone 2.0 HD Battery 1500mAh (Parrot)
 164 connected via standard cable connection. For further information about the technical characteristics of the
 165 SH-P, the reader is referred to Catalano et al. (2014).

166 2.3 Experiments

167 2.3.1 Experiment 1: Testing repeatability of SH-P finger kinematics

168 Experiment 1 was designed to assess the extent to which the SH-P could be used for assistive or
169 rehabilitation purposes by quantifying the repeatability, reliability, and consistency of the SH-P finger
170 movements in free-hand motions. As myoelectric control through a human user could contribute to across-
171 trial variability in SH-P finger kinematics, this experiment removed this potential confound by driving the
172 SH-P through artificial commands. Thus, this design allowed us to isolate the causes of potential variability
173 of SH-P kinematics to its mechanical design.

174 **Apparatus.** The SH-P was placed vertically, fixed to the table through the wrist interface, and connected
175 via a USB-A to Micro USB-B cable to the laptop that was used to send commands to the SH-P and
176 collect data from the on-board hand encoder. We used an active motion tracking system (PhaseSpace
177 Motion Capture system, PhaseSpace Inc.) to record SH-P finger movements through 10 cameras (Optical
178 Resolution: 3600×3600 – Impressive Sub-pixel Resolution: 30000×30000 at 960Hz). We placed a total
179 of 22 light-weight infra-red active LED markers (jitter < 0.5 mm) on the SH-P, including each SH-P
180 “phalanx” and “metacarpo-phalangeal” joints, and on the palm to create a local reference system (Fig. 1-B).
181 For the purpose of this experiment, we analyzed only the markers on the distal phalanges and palm. The
182 orientation of the hand was defined to minimize marker occlusion and maximize capture of all markers by
183 at least 3 cameras for at least 90% of the trial duration.

184 **Experimental protocol.** Custom software was used to control the timing of SH-P finger position (update
185 rate: 8 Hz). We tested a total of sixty-three closing-opening movement cycles that were performed at
186 increasing velocities. The SH-P velocities were expressed in motor steps per sample and ranged from 10
187 steps/sample to 1000 steps/sample. We tested twenty-one SH-P velocities (3 trials per target velocity),
188 corresponding to 10 up to 200 steps per sample with increments of 10 steps/sample, whereas the twenty-first
189 velocity was 1000 steps/sample. Note that 10 steps/sample is the smallest step resolution that can produce
190 an observable change in SH-P finger motion. Although the 1000 step/sample velocity does not capture
191 a realistic SH-P finger velocity associated with activities of daily living, being it faster than the usual
192 velocities the SH-P moves during the normal usage, this velocity was chosen as a stress test of the SH-P
193 hardware. We recorded three-dimensional position of the active markers on the SH-P during all trials.

194 **Data processing and analysis.** When markers occlusion occurred, marker position data were interpolated.
195 We found the most of the marker occlusions occurred at the end of the movement, i.e., at closed fist posture.
196 Therefore, all markers, hence finger kinematics, could be reliably tracked from the initial position (fully
197 open hand) and throughout the entire closing movement, with the exception of a small subset of markers
198 when the hand was fully closed. The next step of kinematic data processing was to transform all marker
199 positions defined with respect to an inertial system of reference, in the local reference frame, defined
200 through the markers attached to the palm of the hand in a triangular arrangement. The new reference frame
201 was defined in order to have the x-axis directed from the little finger side of the hand to the thumb one,
202 with its origin being the center of the base of the triangle. The z-axis was directed from the origin to the
203 upper vertex of the triangle, whereas the y-axis, according to right hand rule, pointed inside the hand (Fig.
204 1-B). The path of the fingertips was visualized in three ways: (1) all paths defined by the markers on the
205 fingers were plotted in 3-dimensional space (Fig. 5); (2) the value of the three-dimensional position of each
206 fingertip was defined with respect to the position of the motor of the SH-P, averaged across trials, and the
207 mean \pm SD values for each fingertip position were plotted (Fig. 6); (3) the position of each fingertip was
208 plotted against time-normalized trial duration (Fig. 7). Using the data processed as described in (2), for

209 each fingertip we computed the Root Mean Square Difference (RMSD) between fingertip position from
210 individual trials and the mean of fingertip position computed across all trials as follows:

$$\text{RMSD} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (\hat{y}_t - y_t)^2}{n}}$$

211 where \hat{y}_t is the sample of the single trial, y_t is the mean of the sample averaged across all trials.

212 2.3.2 Experiment 2: Analysis of EMG signal-to-noise ratio

213 The goal of this experiment was to identify the muscle pair characterized by the highest signal-to-noise
214 (SNR) ratio as a means to reliably compare the performance of three myoelectric controller algorithms
215 (Experiment 3). To allow a realistic comparison with using myoelectric controllers in individuals with
216 upper limb loss, we did not perform an exhaustive search of target muscles to record EMG from to try to
217 minimize cross-talk among adjacent wrist and extrinsic finger muscles, e.g., specific finger compartments
218 within the target finger muscle. Rather, we focused on selecting an agonist-antagonist muscle pair whose
219 EMG activity (1) was characterized by the greatest SNR and (2) could be reliably elicited and recorded
220 across trials when performing reach-to-grasp movements.

221 **Apparatus.** We used two surface EMG electrodes that are commonly used for myoelectric prostheses
222 (linear-proportional 13E200 MYOBOCK electrodes, Otto Bock, Germany). These electrodes are equipped
223 with a logarithmic sensitivity adjustment and high common-mode rejection in the low frequency range
224 ($> 100\text{dB}$ at 50Hz). The electrodes were applied in correspondence of the wrist and finger muscles. We
225 targeted two wrist muscles (m. flexor carpi radialis, FCR, and m. extensor carpi ulnaris, ECU) responsible
226 for wrist flexion and extension, respectively, and two extrinsic finger muscles (m. flexor digitorum
227 superficialis, FDS, and m. extensor digitorum communis, EDC) responsible for finger flexion and extension,
228 respectively. We used a LabView program (National Instruments) to record EMG data (sampling rate: 1
229 kHz).

230 **Experimental protocol.** We asked subjects to reach, grasp, lift, and replace a cylindrical glass bottle
231 (weight: 400 g) whose position was aligned with the right shoulder of the subject on the sagittal plane. In
232 the start position, the subject was instructed to open the hand with the palm parallel to the sagittal plane
233 of the body. The distance between the subject's hand start position and the bottle was 25 cm. We asked
234 subjects to perform two block of reach-go-grasp trials. In the first block (15 trials) subjects performed slow
235 reach-to-grasp movements to be completed within 13 seconds (reach onset to object grasp). In the second
236 block (5 trials), subjects were asked to perform the same movement but at a faster speed such that the
237 whole movement had to be completed within 7 seconds. In each reach-to-grasp trial, subjects were asked to
238 move the hand in a direction perpendicular to her/his body to reach the cylinder. The experimenter gave
239 a "go" signal to cue subjects to start the reach onset. In our instructions to subjects, we emphasized that
240 reach-to-grasp movement should be performed in a natural fashion, i.e., similar to the way one reaches for
241 a cup on a desk. Once the hand had reached the bottle, subjects were asked to grasp, lift ($\sim 1\text{ cm}$ height),
242 hold ($\sim 1\text{ second}$), and replace it on the table, and place the hand back to its start position. We used the
243 same EMG electrode gain for both muscle pairs.

244 **Data processing and analysis.** The data were analyzed by computing the SNR of the EMG signals during
245 the two blocks of reach-to-grasp action and isometric maximal voluntary contractions as

$$\text{SNR}_{dB} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\text{RMS}(\text{Signal})}{\text{RMS}(\text{Noise})}$$

246 where the noise level was measured at rest in-between trials. Noise measurement and SNR computation
247 were performed as described in Solnik et al. (2008). We used the Wilcoxon rank sum test to determine
248 statistically significant differences in the SNR of the two muscle pairs. We computed a pairwise comparison
249 between SNR from finger muscles EMG versus SNR from wrist muscles EMG by pooling all trials (slow
250 and fast) and extensor and flexor muscles within each category.

251 2.3.3 Experiment 3: Identification of optimal myocontroller algorithm

252 The goal of this experiment was to find the most effective EMG mapping algorithm that could generate
253 SH-P finger kinematics during reach-to-grasp movements that best resembled native hand kinematics. To
254 attain this objective, we compared the performance of three EMG-to-SH-P movement mapping algorithms,
255 in terms of effectiveness of movement activation (i.e., the ability of a given algorithm to generate SH-P
256 finger motion) and similarity in the kinematics of SH-P and native hand.

257 **Apparatus.** We used three pairs of identical cylindrical objects (cans) with different radii and weight
258 (52 mm and 250 g; 74 mm and 450 g; 85 mm and 600 g). One of the objects in each pair was to be
259 grasped by the subject with his/her native hand, whereas the object was grasped by the SH-P (Fig. 2). The
260 SH-P grasping movement was controlled by two EMG electrodes placed on the subjects forearm as he/she
261 reached to grasp the target object. The object to be grasped by the subject was positioned on the table
262 surface and aligned with the sagittal plane passing through the subjects right shoulder to avoid large wrist
263 movements. The reach distance between start hand position and target object was 25 cm. The object to be
264 grasped by the SH-P was placed within the palm of the SH-P. View of the SH-P during the reach-to-grasp
265 movement with the native hand was blocked by a screen. To further prevent subjects from getting distracted,
266 they wore headphones with white noise. We used the same motion tracking system used in Experiment 1 to
267 record SH-P and native hand kinematics. The SH-P and native hand were outfitted with markers. For the
268 SH-P, we placed markers on each fingertip (on the back of the third phalanx) and three reference markers
269 on the wrist as done in Experiment 1. On the subject's hand, we placed a marker on the tip of each nail
270 and eight markers on a 3D printed wrist structure taped on the subjects wrist to define a local reference
271 frame (for details see Gabiccini et al. (2013)). Markers were also placed on each of the target objects. As
272 done in Experiment 1, the hand and the objects were positioned to ensure that markers could be viewed
273 by at least 3 cameras. The SH-P parameters were managed through custom software by a laptop. Custom
274 software was also used to record SH-P motor position data. A LabView program (National Instruments),
275 running on a second computer, was used to record EMG and motion tracking data. Data collection by the
276 two computers was synchronized offline via software at 90 Hz.

277 **Experimental protocol.** Before performing the reach-to-grasp experiment and test each of three myoele-
278 ctric algorithms (see below), the SH-P was calibrated by asking subjects to perform a maximal voluntary
279 isometric contraction during finger flexion and extension while recording EMG of each muscle from the
280 target muscle pair (FDS and EDC, respectively). These muscles had been identified in Experiment 2 as
281 those with the highest SNR. The EMG amplitude recorded during calibration is used by the controller to
282 define the threshold EMG amplitude above which finger motion occurs as well as the upper limit of EMG
283 amplitude. The SH-P was mounted horizontally on a support fixed to the table (with the palm parallel to
284 a vertical plane, thumb up) (Fig. 2). To increase the sensitivity of the SH-P to EMG signals, the EMG
285 threshold amplitude obtained with the calibration phase obtained through maximal voluntary contractions

Figure 2. Experiment 3: experimental setup.

286 was reduced to 8% and 14% of the maximum FDS and EDC EMG amplitude recorded. We used the same
 287 EMG electrodes and recording procedures we used in Experiment 2. During calibration the subject sat
 288 in the same position used during the experiment. Once the hand was calibrated, the subject started the
 289 experiment. Subjects performed one block of 60 trials each for each of the three myoelectric controller
 290 algorithms with a 5-minute break between blocks. We tested three EMG controller algorithms. On each
 291 trial, custom software was used to select in a pseudo-random order a given myoelectric controller algorithm
 292 before the start of data collection start. Each algorithm was presented the same number of times. We tested
 293 the following algorithms:

- 294 (1) *EMG Differential*. This EMG-to-motor position mapping uses the difference between the EMG signals
 295 recorded by the two EMG electrodes minus the value of their respective thresholds. The sign of the
 296 EMG amplitude difference dictates the SH-P finger movement direction, whereas the amplitude of the
 297 difference defines finger movement velocity (Fig. 3-A).
- 298 (2) *EMG-First Come First Served (FCFS)*. The first EMG signal that goes over 10% of the maximum
 299 value determined by the calibration procedures defines the direction of SH-P finger movement whereas
 300 its amplitude defines movement velocity. The direction of the movement is inverted if the amplitude of
 301 the leading EMG signal goes below a threshold while the amplitude of the other EMG signal is above
 302 the threshold (Fig. 3-B).
- 303 (3) *EMG-FCFS-Advanced*. This algorithm avoids involuntary inversion of the movement direction by
 304 allowing it only if the amplitude of both EMG signals goes below the threshold (Fig. 3-C).

305 In Figure 4 it is possible to observe how the different algorithms manage the recorded EMG signals on the
 306 SH-P.

307 Each of the three algorithms were presented in two ways that differed depending on whether a modulation

Figure 3. EMG-to-position algorithms implemented on the SH-P. EMG-Differential (A), EMG-FCFS (B) and EMG-FCFS-Advanced (C). EMG1 and EMG2 denote the two signals acquired from the agonist-antagonist muscle pair. THR1 and THR2 denote the threshold for EMG1 and EMG2, respectively. S0, S1, S2 denote the steady position, closing movement, and opening movement, respectively.

308 of the proportional gain, driven by the ratio between the two EMG signals, was implemented. Thus, for
 309 each subject we considered trials with versus without the EMG driven P-gain modulation (see above; Table
 310 1). For the P-gain modulation trials, the proportional gain of the PID controller of the position control of
 311 the motor increased with increasing amplitude of the EMG signal with the smallest amplitude, normalized
 312 to the EMG signal highest amplitude. Upper and lower bounds for the proportional gain were estimated
 313 through pilot data by selecting the range of values in which the SH-P moved smoothly until reaching the
 314 reference position. SH-P movement velocity and impedance were modified by changing the proportional
 315 gain value. The reach-to-grasp task instructions and experimental procedures were the same as those
 316 described for Experiment 2, however no constraint was imposed on the time required to complete the
 317 task. We instructed the subjects to contact the object and exert grip with all the fingers. More specifically,
 318 participants were required to keep their hand with the palm parallel to the sagittal plane and with the
 319 line from the wrist to the middle finger parallel to the transverse plane. During the experiment, subjects
 320 movements were visually inspected by experimenter in order to verify that the aforementioned instructions
 321 were correctly executed. If the experimenter noted any major deviation from the desired behavior, the
 322 trial was repeated. As subjects reached toward the object, the SH-P moved accordingly based on the
 323 EMG-to-position mapping selected for that trial. The three object sizes were presented in a pseudo-random
 324 order and for an equal number of trials for each algorithm.

Figure 4. *Experiment 3:* this picture presents how the different algorithms manage the EMG signals. The plots of the real EMG signals, the EMG signals after the elaboration and the application of the thresholds inside the SH-P firmware and the motor positions are presented. The presented data are obtained during a real trial of Experiment 3.

325 **Data processing and analysis.** For each algorithm, our analysis focused on estimating (1) how many
 326 times the subject was able to activate the SH-P movements with a normal reach-to-grasp action, and (2)
 327 quantifying the similarity between the SH-P and native hand finger kinematics. To define the extent to
 328 which SH-P responded to EMG-based commands, we computed the number of times that EMG signals
 329 could trigger SH-P finger movements. To verify whether EMG signals triggered SH-P finger movement, we
 330 examined the angular position of the motor. Movement activation was defined as the angular position above
 331 the minimum input value required to reach the 25% of the total SH-P movement range. The threshold in
 332 the position of the motor was the only parameter used to discriminate trials with successful from failed
 333 activation of the SH-P. Note that the analysis of the activation rate does not take in account eventual
 334 delays or deactivations after the threshold crossing, this last event will impact the index shown above. For
 335 the identification of the optimal myoelectric controller algorithm, we used trials in which SH-P finger
 336 movements could be generated by EMG signals and quantified the similarity of the paths of the SH-P and
 337 native hand fingertips during reach-to-grasp movements. This analysis consisted of computing a numeric
 338 index between 0 and 1 corresponding to no similarity and identical kinematics between finger movements
 339 in the SH-P and native hand, respectively. The vector distances (three components) between the thumb
 340 and each of the four fingers were computed for both the SH-P and the native hand. These values were
 341 computed for each sample of each trial and normalized by dividing each component of the vector by the
 342 amplitude of the vector itself. This procedure removes the effect of different sizes of the SH-P and native
 343 hand on the comparison of their vector distances. We then computed the dot product between vectors pairs
 344 obtained from the native and artificial hand. The obtained four values, one for each thumb-finger vector,
 345 were summed and divided by 4 to compute the average similarity index. The mean similarity index was
 346 computed for each myoelectric controller algorithm.

3 RESULTS

347 3.1 Experiment 1

Figure 5. *Experiment 1:* path of SH-P fingertip in three dimensional coordinates. Dark and light blue traces denote hand closing and opening paths, respectively.

348 Experiment 1 was designed to assess the consistency of SH-P finger movements across trials and velocities.
 349 Figure 5 shows the three-dimensional coordinates of each fingertip of the SH-P recorded during multiple
 350 hand opening-closing cycles. It can be seen that the fingertip paths during hand opening and closing (dark
 351 and light data points) are fairly consistent across movement cycles. To further visualize the consistency of
 352 fingertip paths, Figure 6 shows these data projected on the three axes of the reference frame and expressed
 353 with respect to the motor angular position.

354 The maximum Root Mean Square Difference (RMSD) across all paths shown in Figure 6 were 9.4 mm
 355 for the thumb (x-axis), 5.7 mm for the index finger (x-axis), 6.5 mm for the middle finger (z-axis), 4.4 mm
 356 for the ring finger (y-axis), and 5 mm for the little finger (y-axis). A high degree of consistency in fingertip
 357 paths can also be appreciated across different movement velocities when plotting finger paths as a function
 358 of normalized time (Fig. 7).

359 Some shifts with respect to time and motor position, considered as offsets, can be observed. This is more
 360 evident in the final phase of the opening of the thumb (x-axis and y-axis), and in the central phase of the
 361 middle finger (z-axis). The data plotted in Figure 6 also show hysteresis in the finger path during hand
 362 opening versus closing movements. However, this hysteresis, which is due to the elastic elements embedded
 363 in the joints that enable the passive opening of the SH-P, does not affect finger path consistency across
 364 trials and movement velocities. The small RMSE of fingertip paths indicate that SH-P finger movements
 365 are very consistent across multiple hand opening-closing cycles and movement velocities.

Figure 6. Experiment 1: spatial position of SH-P fingertips (expressed in the spatial coordinates x, y and z) w.r.t. the angular position of the motor. Black traces in the subplots are the mean closing and opening paths averaged across trials and grey areas denote the standard deviation of the mean path.

366 3.2 Experiment 2

367 The objective of Experiment 2 was to determine the muscle pair characterized by the highest signal-to-
 368 noise ratio (SNR) to be used for comparing myoelectric controllers in Experiment 3. We found that SNR
 369 was significantly greater for the finger than wrist muscles EMG signals (27.73 and 21.88 dB; Wilcoxon
 370 rank sum test: $P = 0.0015$). Therefore, we chose to use the FDS-EDC muscle pair for Experiment 3. This
 371 choice was also motivated by the objective of allowing for a more natural and intuitive myoelectric control
 372 of the SH-P. Indeed, during a reach-to-grasp action, the time course of finger muscles' EMG signals is
 373 closely related to the time course of the SH-P finger motion (Fig. 8). Specifically, the two EDC EMG peaks
 374 correspond with SH-P opening during pre-grasp and at object release at the end of the trial. Similarly, the
 375 FDS EMG signal exhibits a reciprocal activation pattern relative to EDC, i.e., most of its EMG activity
 376 is found between the EDC peaks during SH-P closing. In contrast, this correspondence between EMG
 377 patterns and SH-P finger motion was not being captured by wrist muscles EMG.

378 3.3 Experiment 3

379 Experiment 3 was designed to identify the myoelectric controller algorithm that could elicit SH-P
 380 movements with the greatest degree of consistency and whose kinematics best resembled finger kinematics
 381 of the native hand.

382 Table 1 shows the rate at which each myoelectric controller algorithm could elicit SH-P finger movements.
 383 The EMG mapping algorithm characterized by the highest activation rate was the EMG-Differential
 384 (58.57%), whereas the EMG-FCFS algorithm was characterized by the lowest activation rate (10.12%).

Figure 7. *Experiment 1:* spatial position of the fingertips (expressed in spatial coordinates x, y and z) w.r.t. the time normalized on trial duration.

385 However, even the best performing algorithm failed to generate SH-P movement in a consistent fashion.
 386 Further examination of EMG data revealed that such failure occurred more often in subjects who exhibited
 387 a lower ability to selectively activate one of the two muscles independently from the other and/or to inhibit
 388 muscle activity when switching from hand opening to closing. An important observation was that often
 389 the SH-P responded better to hand-closing than hand-opening EMG signals. This, however, happened
 390 significantly less often when EMG signals were mapped to SH-P movements through the EMG-Differential
 391 algorithm. This could have been due to the fact that, during the object release, subjects not always fully
 392 extended the fingers, but rather relaxed them just enough to trigger object release but not a full extension of
 393 the SH-P fingers. Thus, the EMG amplitude associated with this action might not have been sufficient to
 394 trigger opening of the SH-P.

395 Note that SH-P activation rates were not affected by the implementation of the EMG-driven proportional
 396 gain modulation (PGM, Table 1; chi-squared test = $P > 0.05$).

397 Table 2 shows the similarity index computed on the SH-P and native hand kinematics using only the
 398 trials that successfully elicited SH-P movements as described above.

399 All EMG mapping algorithms resulted in SH-P kinematics that was very similar to native hand kinematics
 400 (range of similarity index: 0.80 to 0.88). We found no statistically significant difference in the similarity
 401 index across the three EMG myoelectric controller algorithms. Taking into account the significantly greater
 402 activation rate for the EMG-Differential algorithm, we conclude that this EMG mapping algorithm is
 403 preferable since it ensures both a more reliable activation of SH-P movement in response to EMG signals
 404 while resembling native hand kinematics.

Figure 8. *Experiment 2:* Time course of EMG activity from finger and wrist muscles (top and bottom row, respectively) as a function of normalized time on the trial duration (“0” and “1” denote the starting moment of the movement of reach and the end of the trial within the predefined time, when the hand was back in starting position, respectively).

4 DISCUSSION

405 The overarching goal of our three experiments was to characterize the performance of a myoelectric hand
 406 prosthesis, the SoftHand-Pro, to assess its feasibility as an assistive and rehabilitative tool. Specifically, we
 407 sought to quantify the extent to which the SH-P finger movements resembled human finger movements. We
 408 reasoned that this factor should be evaluated as it might contribute to the extent to which individuals with
 409 upper limb loss might accept the SH-P as a prosthetic device. To achieve this objective, we also quantified
 410 the consistency of SH-P finger movements and identified the muscles that should be used to extract EMG
 411 signals to control the SH-P. Below we discuss our results and future research directions.

412 *The SH-P mechanical design enables repeatable finger movement kinematics.*

413 Successful control and performance of myoelectric prostheses rely on three factors: (1) the intrinsic
 414 properties of the terminal device (i.e., hardware) which affect how it responds to given EMG signals, (2)
 415 how EMG signals are processed (i.e., software) to generate motion of the terminal device, and (3) the
 416 extent to which the user and his/her motor commands (extracted through EMG signals) can adapt to the
 417 terminal devices hardware and software characteristics. When studying a human subject “in the loop”,
 418 these three factors interact in complex ways, thus making it difficult to understand the role of each factor
 419 on the terminal device performance. To ensure that we could identify the role of each of these three factors
 420 independently, we removed the potential effect of (3) from (1) by driving multiple SH-P movement cycles
 421 through artificial, rather than EMG, control signals (Experiment 1). We should note that, although previous
 422 studies have examined the performance of the SH and SH-P through myoelectric control [Godfrey et al.
 423 (2013), Godfrey et al. (2014), Ajoudani et al. (2014), Zhao et al. (2015), Bonilla et al. (2014)], the present

424 study is the first to examine repeatability of finger kinematics without the confound of trial-to-trial and/or
425 between-subject variability of myoelectrical signals.

426 We found that SH-P finger movements were highly consistent across movement cycles and velocities
427 (Figs. 5-7). Thus, the soft synergy-based design allows the control of 19 degrees of freedom through the
428 action of one motor without compromising the reliability of multi-finger motion. This is an important result
429 when considering the needs of individuals with upper limb loss to perform repeatable hand movements
430 through EMG control. In particular, relying on repeatable kinematics for given EMG inputs should facilitate
431 the adaptation of motor commands/EMG and learning to use the SH-P effectively.

432 *Finger muscles EMG as control signals for the SH-P.*

433 To control multi-fingered hand prostheses through EMG signals, the classic approach is to employ signals
434 collected from multiple muscles and then to use these signals as inputs to machine learning systems. This
435 approach results in creating a direct mapping from multi-EMG patterns and multi-DOF devices [Ison and
436 Artemiadis (2014), Castellini et al. (2009), Tenore et al. (2009)]. In contrast, the design of the SH-P enables
437 the use of a minimal number of EMG signals (two) to control one degree of actuation. However, thanks to
438 its adaptability, the SH-P can exploit the external environment as a multiplier of its DOF, thus enabling the
439 performance of a wide of range of activities of daily living [Centro di Ricerca Enrico Piaggio et al. (2016),
440 Ajoudani et al. (2014), Godfrey et al. (2013), Santello et al. (2016)].

441 Before we could address the question of what myoelectric controller optimizes SH-P performance, we
442 had to identify the muscle pair whose EMG signals was characterized by the greatest signal-to-noise
443 ratio (SNR). As noted for the testing of SH-P finger kinematics repeatability, these questions were not
444 addressed in previous SH-P studies. We found that SNR was significantly greater in finger than wrist
445 muscles. Although the goal of our study was not to perform a systematic evaluation of SNR across many
446 pairs of finger or wrist muscle pairs, this result was important to rule out a potential confound in our
447 evaluation of myoelectric controllers, i.e., negatively biasing the responsiveness of the SH-P to EMG signals
448 or performance of a given myoelectric controller due to using EMG signals with poor SNR. Our EMG
449 data also suggest that, because of the close correspondence between finger flexor/extensor EMG activity
450 patterns and hand opening-closing (Fig. 8), residual finger muscles - if available, and if the quality of EMG
451 signal is acceptable - should be targeted for myoelectric control of hand prostheses. This recommendation
452 is consistent with the above goal of enabling individuals with upper limb loss control a terminal device in a
453 way that closely mimics how they would have controlled their own hand, which may contribute to their
454 acceptance of the hand prosthesis.

455 *Defining the myoelectric controller for optimal reliability and SH-P performance.*

456 Experiment 3 compared the effect of three EMG mapping algorithms for controlling SH-P finger motion
457 during reach-to-grasp. This evaluation was based on the extraction of EMG signals from subjects using
458 their native hand (as done for Experiment 2) while the SH-P was fixed in the proximity to a sensorized
459 object. We found that the EMG-Differential (Fig. 3-A) was the most reliable algorithm for activating
460 SH-P finger motion (59% of trials, Table 1). However, analysis of similarity of SH-P and native hand
461 kinematics revealed that the EMG-FCFS-Advanced algorithm elicited the best performance (Table 2). As
462 no significant statistical difference was found across the three myoelectric controller algorithms, and taking
463 into account the greater ability of activating SH-P finger motion, we conclude that the EMG-Differential
464 algorithm should be used for future studies of SH-P prosthetic applications.

465 The superiority of the EMG-Differential algorithm over the other two algorithms can be explained taking
466 into account the criteria underlying each EMG-to-position algorithm. The EMG-FCFS and the EMG-
467 FCFS-Advanced algorithms both rely on the existence of an EMG threshold. Specifically, the threshold
468 is used to manage the signals by choosing the leading one and the direction of the movement. However,
469 this threshold cannot be adjusted while operating the SH-P to guarantee the correct functioning of the
470 algorithm. For this work we selected the thresholds after analyzing previous recorded EMG signals path
471 (during Experiment 2) such that to permit to the SH-P to move also in presence of weak EMG signals. The
472 choice of a lower threshold would have resulted negative effects due to the noise recorded by the sEMG
473 electrodes. This feature can account for the very low percentage of SH-P activations, since the signals
474 generated during normal hand use did not result always strong enough to exceed the threshold. In contrast,
475 as the EMG-Differential control scheme does not use an EMG threshold. Therefore, any signal, even if it is
476 small, could activate SH-P finger movements.

477 With regard to the EMG-Differential, although this algorithm was characterized by the highest SH-P
478 activation rate, it was not close to 100%. We believe that this is due to the fact that EMG signals were
479 recorded during a natural reach-to-grasp movement with the native hand, rather than subjects attempting to
480 move the SH-P through EMG signals. Furthermore, subjects were prevented from viewing the SH-P during
481 the task and were therefore unaware of whether or how the SH-P moved. This was done to further remove
482 the potential confound of EMG signals adapting to visual feedback of SH-P performance. Whereas this is
483 a desirable phenomenon in terminal device training, for the purpose of the study we had to remove this
484 potential confound to focus on the ability of natural EMG activation patterns to elicit SH-P movements.
485 Therefore, we believe that the percentage of trials characterized by SH-P activation could significantly
486 increase by having subjects adapt their EMG activation patterns to viewing the SH-P during reach-to-grasp
487 tasks.

488 Lastly, we also examined the effect of P-gain modulation on myoelectric controller performance as it can
489 influence movement velocity, i.e., increasing the proportional gain of the PID controller of the SH-P could
490 allow for a better trajectory tracking. We found that EMG drive P-gain modulation had no effect on the
491 similarity between SH-P and native hand kinematics. Therefore, this technique could be used to enable
492 other SH-P features, such as impedance control of the hand during interaction with objects [Ajoudani et al.
493 (2014)], without affecting the similarity with human finger kinematics.

5 CONCLUSIONS

494 Our results support the feasibility and potential of the SH-P as an effective hand prosthesis for individuals
495 with upper limb loss. Specifically, we found that the mechanical design of the SoftHand-Pro, combined with
496 using EMG from finger muscles through the appropriate EMG myocontroller algorithm (EMG differential),
497 enables a reliable motion of all SH-P digits through EMG recorded from only two finger muscles. A
498 particularly encouraging result, which we believe is unique in the literature of hand prostheses, is that
499 EMG-driven motion of SH-P fingers is very similar to native hand kinematics. This is important because,
500 given the high abandonment rate of upper limb prostheses, the movement and design anthropomorphism
501 of the SH-P may contribute to greater acceptance of prostheses by individuals with upper limb loss. We
502 should also point out that the SH-P anthropomorphism offers great potential for using the SH-P as a novel
503 assistive and sensorimotor rehabilitation device for individuals affected by neurological disorders, e.g.
504 using the SH-P as a supernumerary limb [Prattichizzo et al. (2014)].
505 While this work focuses on the control of SH-P, future work will address the usage of multi-EMG inputs

506 (see Santello et al. (2016) for a review on this topic) for the control of multiple degrees of actuation, which
507 were already implemented in a new purely robotic version of the SH [Della Santina et al. (2015)].

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

508 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
509 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

510 SF, MB, AB, and MS designed the study. GG implemented the controllers of the SoftHand Pro. SF, MB,
511 JS, JSPN, and SB performed the experiments and data analysis. All authors contributed to writing the
512 manuscript.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

521 In this section are exposed the abbreviations used within the text of this work.

- 522 - **Ag-Aag**, Agonist-Antagonist;
- 523 - **DOF**, Degree of freedom;
- 524 - **ECU**, Extensor Carpi Ulnaris;
- 525 - **EDC**, Extensor Digitorum Communis;
- 526 - **EMG**, Electromyography;
- 527 - **FCR**, Flexor Carpi Radialis;
- 528 - **FDS**, Flexor Digitorum Superficialis;
- 529 - **ML**, Machine Learning;
- 530 - **PGM**, P-gain Modulation
- 531 - **RMSD**, Root Mean Square Difference;
- 532 - **SD**, Standard Deviation;
- 533 - **sEMG**, surface Electromyography;
- 534 - **SH**, Pisa/IIT SoftHand;
- 535 - **SH-P**, SoftHand Pro;
- 536 - **SNR**, Signal-to-Noise Ratio.

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FIGURE LABELS

640 In this section are reported the figure labels.

641 **Figure 1:** SH-P used for Experiments 1 and 3. A: Dimensions of SH-P and the main components. B:
642 Markerization protocol (Experiment 1). Note that only the markers placed on the distal phalanges were
643 used for the experiment, whereas additional markers in a triangular configuration were placed on the palm
644 (not visible in this picture).

645 **Figure 2:** *Experiment 3*: experimental setup.

646 **Figure 3:** EMG-to-position algorithms implemented on the SH-P. EMG-Differential (A), EMG-FCFS
647 (B) and EMG-FCFS-Advanced (C). EMG1 and EMG2 denote the two signals acquired from the agonist-
648 antagonist muscle pair. THR1 and THR2 denote the threshold for EMG1 and EMG2, respectively. S0, S1,
649 S2 denote the steady position, closing movement, and opening movement, respectively.

650 **Figure 4:** *Experiment 3*: this picture presents how the different algorithms manage the EMG signals. The
651 plots of the real EMG signals, the EMG signals after the elaboration and the application of the thresholds
652 inside the SH-P firmware and the motor positions are presented. The presented data are obtained during a
653 real trial of Experiment 3.

654 **Figure 5:** *Experiment 1*: path of SH-P fingertip in three dimensional coordinates. Dark and light blue
655 traces denote hand closing and opening paths, respectively.

656 **Figure 6:** *Experiment 1*: spatial position of SH-P fingertips (expressed in the spatial coordinates x, y and
657 z) w.r.t. the angular position of the motor. Black traces in the subplots are the mean closing and opening
658 paths averaged across trials and grey areas denote the standard deviation of the mean path.

659 **Figure 7:** *Experiment 1*: spatial position of the fingertips (expressed in spatial coordinates x, y and z)
660 w.r.t. the time normalized on trial duration.

661 **Figure 8:** *Experiment 2*: time course of EMG activity from finger and wrist muscles (top and bottom
662 row, respectively) as a function of normalized time on the trial duration (“0” and “1” denote the starting
663 moment of the movement of reach and the end of the trial within the predefined time, when the hand was
664 back in starting position, respectively).

TABLES

Table 1. *Experiment 3:* activation rate with the different algorithms, considering (W PGM) and discarding (W/o PGM) the proportional gain modulation. Motion was considered successfully activated when SH-P motor position reached or overcame 25% of the whole range.

Subj	EMG-Diff			EMG-FCFS			EMG-FCFS-Adv		
	Tot	W/o PGM	W PGM	Tot	W/o PGM	W PGM	Tot	W/o PGM	W PGM
1	98.33%	96.67%	100.00%	15.00%	10.00%	20.00%	40.00%	26.67%	53.33%
2	68.33%	66.67%	70.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	1.67%	3.33%	0.00%
3	88.33%	86.67%	90.00%	41.67%	46.67%	36.67%	30.00%	33.33%	26.67%
4	5.00%	6.67%	3.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	11.67%	23.33%	0.00%
5	86.67%	80.00%	93.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	3.33%	0.00%	6.67%
6	26.67%	36.67%	16.67%	1.67%	3.33%	0.00%	3.33%	6.67%	0.00%
7	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	10.00%	10.00%	10.00%	5.00%	0.00%	10.00%
8	8.33%	16.67%	0.00%	5.00%	10.00%	0.00%	21.67%	26.67%	16.67%
9	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	5.00%	10.00%	0.00%	5.00%	0.00%	10.00%
10	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	3.33%	0.00%	6.67%	3.33%	3.33%	3.33%
11	88.33%	83.33%	93.33%	40.00%	43.33%	36.67%	55.00%	50.00%	60.00%
12	91.67%	90.00%	93.33%	3.33%	3.33%	3.33%	15.00%	13.33%	16.67%
13	58.33%	63.33%	53.33%	3.33%	3.33%	3.33%	15.00%	13.33%	16.67%
14	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	13.33%	16.67%	10.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Mean	58.57%	59.05%	58.09%	10.12%	11.19%	9.05%	15.00%	14.29%	15.72%

Table 2. *Experiment 3:* kinematic similarity index between SH-P and real user movements, for the different mapping algorithms, considering (W PGM) and discarding (W/o PGM) the proportional gain modulation. A score close to 1 indicates a high level of similarity. The absent data are relative to the conditions with activation rate 0%. Indeed, in this analysis we only considered trials where the SH-P was activated.

Subj	EMG-Diff		EMG-FCFS		EMG-FCFS-Adv	
	W/o PGM	W PGM	W/o PGM	W PGM	W/o PGM	W PGM
1	0.8840	0.8848	0.9337	0.9381	0.9598	0.8242
2	0.8157	0.8446	—	—	0.9014	—
3	0.8306	0.8369	0.8144	0.8398	0.7844	0.8094
4	0.7565	0.7029	—	—	0.8646	—
5	0.8218	0.8489	—	—	—	0.7557
6	0.7888	0.8348	0.8086	—	0.9357	—
7	0.7344	0.7489	0.6389	0.7271	—	0.6768
8	0.7985	—	0.8441	—	0.8394	0.8318
9	—	—	0.9284	—	—	0.7624
10	—	—	—	0.8296	0.9050	0.7624
11	0.8225	0.8027	0.9075	0.8256	0.8593	0.8716
12	0.8833	0.8868	0.9784	0.8743	0.8942	0.9091
13	0.6976	0.6907	0.6506	0.8224	0.8530	0.7845
14	0.8885	0.8914	0.9121	0.9173	—	—
Mean	0.8102	0.8158	0.8417	0.8468	0.8797	0.7988